

Sleep Disorders and Alzheimer's Disease - Mechanisms and Treatment

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Abstract Alzheimer's disease is the most common cause of dementia in the elderly and has a multifactorial pathogenesis. In recent years, attention has been directed toward sleep disturbances as an important, modifiable risk factor for its development and progression. The purpose of this article is to discuss the current state of knowledge regarding the relationship between sleep disorders and the course of Alzheimer's disease. The search was conducted based on The Cochrane, PubMed, Medline, and Google Scholar databases. Publications in English that met thematic and substantive criteria were analyzed. Ultimately, 41 publications were included in the review. Alzheimer's disease is the most common cause of dementia in older adults. It leads to progressive cognitive decline and significant difficulties in daily functioning. Modifiable risk factors include lifestyle, low education, social isolation, unhealthy eating habits, tobacco use, alcohol intake, low physical activity, and disturbances in sleep. To date, no disease-modifying treatments exist. Possible treatment options include pharmacological and psychological therapies. Poor sleep in patients with Alzheimer's disease has been shown to contribute to the accumulation of pathological proteins through impaired glymphatic system function, circadian rhythm disruption, and increased inflammation in the central nervous system, what leads to cognitive decline. Both pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions, such as cognitive behavioural therapy, light exposure, and regular physical activity, have been proven to be effective. Early diagnosis and correction of sleep disorders may be an important element of Alzheimer's disease prevention and treatment.

Keywords: Alzheimer disease, sleep disorders, tau protein, amyloid

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common cause of dementia among people aged 65 years and older [1]. Epidemiological studies indicate that in 2021, approximately 57 million people worldwide suffered from dementia, most of whom lived in low- and middle-income countries. To date, nearly 10 million new cases occur every year. The most common cause of dementia is AD, which is estimated to constitute 60-70% of the cases [2]. It is characterized by progressive cognitive decline, with impairments in recent memory, language and motor functions, and visual-spatial orientation. Worsening of mental functions, such as emotional disturbances, impulse disinhibition, and recurrent positive symptoms, can also be present. It can all lead to significant difficulties in performing daily activities, including complete inability to live independently [3]. Currently, there are no medications that modify the course of AD [1]. The search for modifiable risk factors has become an important goal of scientific research in the 21st century [4]. The pathogenesis of AD is not fully understood. Many theories contradict each other [5]. It is currently recognised that the mechanism of disease development is multifactorial. Modifiable risk factors include lifestyle

diseases, low education, social exclusion, poor diet, smoking, alcohol consumption, low physical activity, and sleep disorders [2,6]. Among non-modifiable factors, genetic factors, age, gender, and family history can be mentioned [7]. The purpose of this article is to discuss the current state of knowledge regarding the relationship between sleep disorders and the course of Alzheimer's disease.

METHODS

A literature review was conducted. We focused on articles published between 2017 and 2025. We used databases such as Cochrane, PubMed, Medline, and Google Scholar and considered only full-text articles in English. In substantively justified cases, we also included older articles. The search was performed using keywords concerning pathophysiology, epidemiology, symptoms, and treatment of Alzheimer's disease, the connection between sleep and Alzheimer's disease, treatment of sleep disorders in patients with Alzheimer's disease, and the glymphatic system. Article selection was conducted individually, beginning with the keyword and abstract, followed by a detailed analysis of the full texts that met the inclusion criteria. Exclusion criteria included case reports and non-peer-reviewed sources. Publications not directly related to the research topic were rejected. Finally, the publications were assessed for timeliness, relevance to the study's topic, and substantive value. Ultimately, 41 publications were included in the review.

RESULTS

A. Sleep Disorders in Alzheimer's Disease

Sleep disorders (SD) are frequently observed in individuals with AD and constitute a very troublesome problem for their caregivers [8]. In those patients, SD can manifest itself in various ways, including excessive sleepiness, shortened sleep duration, circadian rhythm reversal, or sleep apnea. Sleep efficiency, amount of slow-wave sleep (SWS), and the share of fast waves in rapid-eye-movement sleep (REM) can be significantly lowered. On the other hand, sleep latency and REM sleep latency may be increased. Disturbed circadian rhythms alone can lead to cognitive disorders. It is worth noting that AD onset precedes the alteration of cognitive functions by 10-15 years [9]. Long before they appear, part of correctly structured, soluble amyloid- β ($A\beta$) becomes insoluble and accumulates in the form of amyloid plaques. Sleep disturbances can emerge very early as the brain's regions responsible for the sleep-wake rhythm are usually among the first ones affected by the disease. That is why sleep disorders often precede cognitive dysfunctions. In general, people with mild cognitive impairment, with or without AD, show abnormalities in electroencephalography during sleep, like a reduced amount of SWS or fewer sleep spindles. Historically, SD have been viewed as a consequence of neurodegenerative processes in the central nervous system. However, more recent papers suggest a bidirectional pathophysiological relationship, in which SD may be both a consequence of AD and a promoter of abnormal protein accumulation and disease progression [9–12].

B. Mechanisms

The impact of disordered sleep on the genesis of AD is complex. The main groups of factors influencing the development and progression of the disease include impaired metabolic clearance, impaired metabolism of pathogenic proteins, and the occurrence of neuroinflammation [9, 10, 13].

1. Glymphatic Clearance and Pathogenesis of Alzheimer's Disease

A new era in brain physiology research began with the discovery of the glymphatic system in 2012 [13]. Before, it was thought that the central nervous system (CNS) was totally deprived of a lymphatic system, as it completely lacks conventional lymphatic vessels. In general, the lymphatic system is crucial for the homeostasis of tissues. Fluids, proteins, and soluble materials, notably the products of metabolism, are returned to general circulation via lymphatic vessels. The glymphatic system is found in the CNS. It relies on cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) flowing along peri-arterial spaces into the brain interstitium, where it mixes with interstitial fluid to remove soluble waste products. This fluid then drains along the perivascular spaces, eventually returning to the general circulation. One of its functions is the clearance of neurotoxic metabolites from the interstitial space, including $A\beta$ and Tau proteins [14]. When the efficiency of glymphatic clearance decreases, concentrations of $A\beta$ and Tau protein increase, which elevates the risk of accumulation [9, 13]. Deposition of those abnormal proteins in brain tissue in the form of plaques is considered one of the most characteristic symptoms of AD [15]. Currently, the relationship between beta-amyloid and the pathogenesis of AD is not fully understood. One popular hypothesis is the "amyloid cascade" theory, which posits that the deposition of beta-amyloid in fibrillar form has a toxic effect on neurons and leads to their death [15, 16]. What is more, studies have shown that incorrectly structured, and therefore insoluble, hyperphosphorylated Tau protein accumulates in neurons, causing microtubule degradation. Intracellular transport is disrupted, leading to synapse loss and, ultimately, cell death [15, 17, 18].

During SWS interstitial space increases by up to 60% compared to wakefulness [19]. Metabolite clearance by the glymphatic system is most active during this sleep phase [20]. The results of numerous studies indicate that sleep deprivation or its fragmentation leads to a decrease in the efficiency of glymphatic $A\beta$ clearance [20–22]. Its accumulation occurs in a sleep-dependent manner. Even one night of sleep deprivation can lead to an increase in $A\beta$ concentration in the cerebrospinal fluid in

healthy individuals and significantly elevated A β accumulation [23, 24]. Furthermore, a small share of SWS in total sleep duration and decreased sleep continuity are associated with increased brain amyloid burden. This supports the role of sleep in the pathogenesis of AD [24]. On one hand, sleep deprivation increases neuronal activity, which is associated with increased production of beta-amyloid [15, 24]. On the other hand, disturbed sleep promotes hyperphosphorylation of the Tau protein [17]. Sleep deprivation has been shown to positively correlate with elevated levels of Tau protein in the CSF and interstitial space [25]. Reports suggest that Tau protein dysregulation may be an early consequence of SD and accelerate the formation of insoluble neurofibrillary tangles [26].

2. Inflammation and the Circadian Rhythm

The regulation of circadian rhythms is closely linked to the regulation of inflammatory processes in the brain. The relationship is bidirectional [27, 28]. Sleep-wake rhythm disturbances are often observed in patients with AD [8]. Chronic SD, by disrupting the circadian rhythm, can lead to chronic inflammation in the nervous tissue. Research indicates that the accumulation of beta-amyloid (A β) and tau protein promotes the activation of microglia and astrocytes, which leads to increased production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1beta and tumour necrosis factor alpha [17, 29]. This inflammation, in turn, impairs synaptic plasticity and accelerates neurodegeneration and the aggregation of pathological proteins such as A β and Tau. These processes exacerbate each other, thus creating a vicious cycle linking AD and neurodegeneration [17].

3. Disturbance of Other Sleep Functions

Sleep plays a key role in maintaining the body's homeostasis in the context of maintaining normal cognitive functions. It influences, among other things, synaptic plasticity, learning and memory processes, and maintaining the conditions necessary for a healthy state of wakefulness [19]. Research indicates that both REM and non-rapid eye movement (NREM) sleep phases are where emotional and procedural memory consolidation occurs, and their disruption leads to cognitive decline [30, 31]. Disturbances in this phase lead to cognitive decline, as observed in patients with dementia [32]. Research suggests that NREM sleep phase disturbances also contribute to the progression of AD and are associated with increased brain amyloid burden. Slow wave disturbances during this phase contribute to astrocyte dysfunction, which in turn may be associated with impaired A β clearance. On the other hand, deposition of A β and Tau proteins in numerous brain regions leads to disturbances in the NREM phase [33]. Other authors also indicate a link between obstructive sleep apnea and an increased risk of neurodegeneration due to hypoxia and increased oxidative stress [34]. Oxidative stress is a well-known factor in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease [18].

4. Sleep Duration and Alzheimer's Disease

Both too long and not enough sleep lead to substantial consequences. Even one night of sleep deprivation leads to increased amyloid burden, as measured with the use of positron emission tomography and 18F-florbetaben [24]. On the other sleep duration longer than 8 hours was associated with 2-fold higher risk of developing AD [35]. What is more, Joseph R. Winer et al. conducted a study including 4417 participants. Many variables, such as sex, age, race or ethnicity and years of education were taken under consideration. Participants were divided into three groups, according to duration of sleep: short duration sleep (6 hours or less), normal duration sleep (7-8 hours) and long duration sleep (9 hours or more). They found out that short sleep during the night led to higher A β burden [36].

C. Clinical Significance and Treatment Options

Behavioral and pharmacological interventions may be considered in the treatment of sleep disorders in patients with AD. Cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia improves sleep and cognitive functions [37-39]. In the treatment of SD, maintaining good sleep hygiene is crucial, including carrying on a regular sleep schedule, sufficient exposure to bright light, and engaging in physical activity [38, 39]. Research suggests that this type of therapy has little potential effectiveness in patients with already present severe AD symptoms. Nevertheless, treating sleep disorders should be considered one of the primary ways to prevent disease progression [37]. In Table 1., we present practical solutions that may be put to use in everyday life (Table 1).

Table 1. Actions recommended to improve sleep in patients with Alzheimer's disease

Problem	Solution
Problems falling asleep or trouble sleeping at night	Limit napping to a short nap in the early afternoon.
Waking up due to a suboptimal temperature	Check if sleeping areas have a comfortable temperature, and remember to avoid overheating.
Difficulty falling asleep due to circadian rhythm disturbances caused by suboptimal light exposure.	Promote consistent exposure to natural or bright light in the morning and evening. Ensure that living spaces are well-lit during the day while keeping bedrooms dark at night. Use nightlights in bathrooms to prevent the need for bright overhead lighting during nighttime trips.
Shallow sleep and waking up too easily	Eliminate or reduce environmental factors that may interrupt sleep.
Difficulty falling asleep caused by stimulating substances.	Limit or avoid consumption of alcohol, caffeine (including chocolate), and nicotine.
Awakening due to the need to urinate	Limit fluid intake in the evening and ensure the bladder is emptied before bedtime. For those experiencing nocturia, planned nighttime bathroom visits may be beneficial.
Awakening due to hunger	Set consistent times for meals, including bedtime snack if necessary. Use sleep-promoting foods like milk, bananas, or cheese.
Sleep problems due to insufficient physical activity	Encourage the patient to participate in regular physical activity suited to their cognitive abilities.
Patient wakes up to watch television	Advise patients who wake up during the night to avoid watching television.
Problems with sleeping when faced with changes in daily routine	Plan in advance and schedule calm, restful periods following any unusual or special activities.

Source: [30]

Changing the activity routines of patients with dementia can be challenging for their caregivers due to a general deterioration of the patient's well-being. Alterations in daily routines, including family gatherings or holidays, may lead to greater confusion and deterioration of nighttime sleep quality. It is also worth noting that sleep disturbances might have different backgrounds, depending on where a patient lives on a daily basis. At home, sleep disruptions can be caused by factors such as pets in the bedroom, adult children or grandchildren living in the same space, caregiver snoring, watching TV in the bedroom, and external traffic noise. In care facilities, disturbances may stem from loud conversations by staff, the noise of medication carts being moved through hallways, and disruptive roommates. Clinicians should provide the patient's family with personalized, precise recommendations. For the results to be achieved and maintained over time, a strong rationale and guidance throughout the process is necessary [30].

Many medications can contribute to insomnia. These include beta-blockers, bronchodilators, corticosteroids, gastrointestinal medications, cardiac medications, and neurological medications [30].

Pharmacological treatment for insomnia in Alzheimer's disease includes medications that regulate circadian rhythms, such as melatonin, tricyclic antidepressants, benzodiazepines, zolpidem, and classic and atypical antipsychotics [30, 39]. We presented some of the pharmaceuticals and nutraceuticals that have a therapeutic effect concerning SD in individuals with AD in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Pharmacological treatment of sleep disturbances in Alzheimer's disease

Group	Examples	Effects
Pharmacological treatments		
Tryptophan derivative	Melatonin	Improvement in sleep efficiency
Atypical tetracyclic antidepressants	Mirtazapine	Improvement in the quality of sleep
Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors	Trazodone	Effective for insomnia, has an antidepressant effect
Dual orexin receptor antagonists	Suvorexant Lemborexant	Extend the duration of night sleep
Antipsychotic agents	Risperidone	Improves sleep, lowers agitation
Benzodiazepines	Zopiclone Zolpidem Zaleplon	Lower sleep latency and frequency of awakenings, sedative effect
Tetracyclin antidepressants	Mianserin	Improvement in the quality of sleep
Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors	Donepezil Galantamine Rivastigmine	Improvement in sleep quality
Benzodiazepine derivative	Clonazepam	Highly effective for treating the symptoms of rapid eye movement behaviour disorder

Source: [30, 39, 40]

Table 3. Pharmacological treatment of sleep disturbances in Alzheimer's disease

Group	Examples	Effects
Nutraceuticals		
	Caffeine	Reduction of excessive sleepiness
	Chamomile	Anxiolytic effect
	Cherries and cherry Juice	Regulates and improves sleep
	Kava Kava	Alleviates depressive and anxiety symptoms
	L-Tryptophan	Lowers sleep latency and increases sleepiness perceived by the patient
	Valerian	Sedative effect

Source: [39]

Treatment of comorbid psychiatric conditions, such as depression, is also important because they can contribute to sleep and circadian rhythm disturbances independent of AD [30, 39]. Based on the publication "The effect of light therapy on sleep disorders and psychobehavioral symptoms in patients with Alzheimer's disease: A meta-analysis", light therapy was found to offer significant benefits. Compared to standard care, it demonstrated improved sleep efficiency, better circadian rhythm stability, and reduced variability in daily activity. Furthermore, a reduction in patients' symptoms of depression and agitation was observed, as well as a reduction in caregiver burden [41]. Behavioural interventions in the form of physical exercise in individuals with Alzheimer's disease have shown beneficial effects on sleep and cognitive function. They improve sleep quality, both subjectively and objectively, as measured by polysomnography or actigraphy [38].

DISCUSSION

Early diagnosis and treatment of sleep disorders in patients with Alzheimer's Disease is a modifiable therapeutic target to delay or slow Alzheimer's disease progression by restoring physiological sleep and reducing neurotoxic accumulation. When assessing the presence of sleep disorders, it is important to consider not only the duration and regularity of sleep rhythms, but also the quality and proportion of the slow phase. The approach to treatment of SD in patients with AD should be multidisciplinary and take into account daily routines, the patient's environment and medications. To achieve better results, family and caregivers should be instructed on how to create a proper environment and routines for patients with SD and implement the recommendations in the daily care.

AD is the leading cause of dementia, characterised by progressive cognitive decline and functional impairment. Recent research has highlighted the complex, bidirectional relationship between SD and AD. Sleep disturbances, such as insomnia, circadian rhythm disruption, reduced sleep duration, and sleep apnea, occur frequently in AD and may both result from and contribute to its progression. One of the key mechanisms involves dysfunction of the glymphatic system, responsible for clearing metabolic waste products, including A β and Tau protein. Sleep deprivation and fragmentation reduce glymphatic clearance efficiency, promoting the accumulation of these neurotoxic proteins. Moreover, disturbed sleep increases neuronal activity and tau hyperphosphorylation, accelerating neurofibrillary tangle formation. Disruption of circadian rhythms enhances neuroinflammation through activation of microglia and astrocytes, with increased production of cytokines, such as IL-1 β and TNF- α . This inflammatory response further impairs synaptic plasticity and amplifies neurodegeneration. Both short - shorter than 6 hours, and long - longer than 9 hours, sleep durations are associated with greater A β deposition and higher AD risk. Restoration of normal sleep architecture, especially SWS, appears crucial for metabolic clearance and memory consolidation. Behavioural interventions, including cognitive behavioural therapy for insomnia, light therapy, and regular physical activity, improve sleep

quality and cognitive function. Pharmacological options such as melatonin or circadian-regulating agents may complement these approaches.

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